

Abstract

- 1) Scientific applications relying in GNSS we need accurate phase measurements, which may be difficult to obtain under harsh propagation conditions.
- 2) In the case of ionospheric scintillation monitoring (ISM), phase measurements are only available from expensive (static) dedicated receivers.
- 3) In this article, we propose a new approach for low-cost scintillation phase estimation.
- 4) We discuss the possible extension to moving platforms, which would be a significant improvement with respect to commercial ionospheric monitoring receivers, because it would allow to have observables over oceanic regions within an affordable cost.
- 5) The proposed approach is tested with real scintillation (recorded over Hanoi in 2015) and clock-phase (HackRF TCXO) data.

Key words

- Ionospheric scintillation
- Space weather monitoring
- GNSS receiver design
- Carrier synchronization
- Low-cost GNSS receivers

The Idea & Methodology Overview

Standard ISM techniques focus on one-satellite-at-a-time processing: clock-induced phase errors are unobservable under ionospheric phase scintillation.

If we are able to detect at least one scintillation-free satellite link, from where we can estimate the clock phase contribution, then we can obtain a good ionospheric scintillation estimation from other satellite links after clock compensation.

Scintillation & Clock Phase AR Approximation

The proposed AR model approximation:

$$\rho_{s,k} = \sum_{i=1}^q \gamma_i \rho_{s,k-i} + \kappa + \eta_{\rho,k}, \quad \eta_{\rho,k} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\eta_{\rho}}^2)$$

$$\theta_{s,k} = \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i \theta_{s,k-i} + \eta_{\theta_s,k}, \quad \eta_{\theta_s,k} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\eta_{\theta_s}}^2),$$

$$\theta_{c,k} = \sum_{i=1}^l \psi_i \theta_{c,k-i} + \eta_{\theta_c,k}, \quad \eta_{\theta_c,k} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\eta_{\theta_c}}^2),$$

$\{\gamma_i, \beta_i, \psi_i\}$ are the set of AR coefficients, and $\{\sigma_{\eta_{\rho}}^2, \sigma_{\eta_{\theta_s}}^2, \sigma_{\eta_{\theta_c}}^2\}$ the driving noise variances. $\{q, p, l\}$ are the AR model order. Two problems arise: i) how to decide the correct model order, and ii) how to obtain the AR coefficients. In general, both model order and coefficients can be obtained by standard time-series analysis and off-line fitting to synthetic or real data.

State-space Model Formulation & EKF Architecture

Using the standard 3rd order LOS phase model, $\theta_{d,k} \approx \theta_0 + 2\pi(f_{d,k}kT_s + f_{r,k}k^2T_s^2/2)$, and the AR approximation, it is possible to write a state-space model formulation of the carrier tracking problem and the corresponding extended Kalman filter (EKF) solution. See the full paper and [1] for details.

[1] J. Vilà-Valls, P. Closas and J. T. Curran, "Multi-frequency GNSS Robust Carrier Tracking for Ionospheric Scintillation Mitigation", Journal of Space Weather and Space Climate, vol. 7, A26, October 2017. DOI: 10.1051/swsc/2017020.

Computer simulations

(Left) Estimated clock phase-induced error with an EKF considering an AR(3) clock model. Mean RMSE = 0.0365 rad.

(Right) Computed σ_{ϕ} values for a 10 minute period of strong phase and amplitude scintillation including the reference, uncompensated, and clock-corrected estimates of the phase scintillation index, respectively denoted: $\sigma_{\phi,ref}$, $\sigma_{\phi,clk}$ and $\sigma_{\phi,cor}$.

Real Scintillation & Clock Phase Data

(Left) Severe ionospheric scintillation event recorded over Hanoi in 2015.

(Right) TCXO clock phase-induced error in cycles.

GNSS & Ionospheric Scint Signal Model

The baseband generic GNSS transmitted signal can be expressed as

$$s(t) = \sqrt{2P_x(t)}d(t - \tau(t))c(t - \tau(t))e^{j\theta(t)}, \quad \theta(t) = 2\pi f_d(t) + \theta_e(t) \quad (1)$$

The behavior of scintillation onto GNSS signals: multiplicative channel

$$x(t) = \xi_s(t)s(t) + w(t), \quad \xi_s(t) = \rho_s(t)e^{j\theta_s(t)} \quad (2)$$

Simplified model at the input of the carrier phase tracking stage:

$$y_k = \alpha_k e^{j\theta_k} + n_k, \quad n_k \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{n,k}^2) \quad (3)$$

Case 1) scint-free satellite link, $\theta_k = \theta_{d,k} + \theta_{c,k}$, $\alpha_k = A_k$

Case 2) scint-corrupted link: $\theta_k = \theta_{d,k} + \theta_{s,k} + \theta_{c,k}$, $\alpha_k = A_k \rho_{s,k}$

Scenario #1) scintillation amplitude/phase tracking without clock-phase error (benchmark).

Scenario #2) scintillation amplitude/phase tracking with a clock phase-induced error, compensated with the output of the EKF running on the scintillation-free satellite link.

Scenario #3) scintillation amplitude/phase tracking without clock compensation.

	Scenario #1	Scenario #2	Scenario #3
RMSE	0.0318	0.0390	1.6955

Mean RMSE (rad) for the estimation of a severe scintillation event at L1 C/A.

Conclusions & Future Work

- We proposed a new EKF-based carrier tracking architecture for low-cost ISM.
- Promising results using real data were obtained for the static receiver case.
- This opens the door for the efficient design of software-defined ISM receivers in non-static scenarios.
- The extension to moving platforms & adaptive model learning need to be further investigated.